

FINDING REGIONS OF SCIENTIFIC AND OPERATIONAL INTEREST FOR A EUROPEAN LUNAR EXPLORATION INFRASTRUCTURE. C. Orgel¹, F. McDonald¹, G. Consuma¹, M. J. Losekamm¹, A. Oetting¹ and J. Carpenter¹, ¹European Space Research and Technology Centre (ESTEC), European Space Agency, Noordwijk, NL (csilla.orgel@ext.esa.int).

Introduction: By 2040, the European Space Agency (ESA) aims to lead a robotic lunar base, which will work in synergy with human exploration. In June 2025, ESA released a call for evidence regarding possible Regions of Interest (ROI) for a European-led lunar infrastructure, which would be deployed from the early 2030s. The received evidence was reviewed and discussed in a community workshop which took place on 15th September 2025.

Criteria for Identification of ROI: The community was asked to identify regions that have

- Access to high geological diversity to enable fundamental scientific investigations into the origin, evolution, and current environment of the Moon [1]
- Access to diverse potential resources to facilitate systematic sampling and in-situ assessment of their utilisation potential [2, 3]
- Proximity to subsurface features which could be used as shelter, such as pits and lava tubes, to enable habitation and environment studies [4]
- Scalability to allow rapid high-impact science return from the earliest missions, with substantial potential for longer term science return
- Potential impacts on crew health, including psychological well-being.

Summary of Key Findings: 33 submissions were received. From these submissions, 26 different regions were proposed, 18 were located on the nearside (*Figure 1*), four in the south polar region, and four on the far side. No regions of interest were submitted for the north pole. These findings highlight the key aspects and criteria that should be prioritized in the selection of the site for the infrastructure, not only to support exploration but also to enable meaningful scientific activities.

Major scientific themes:

- Geological diversity is a primary driver in selecting a region. Diverse terrains promise the highest scientific return, preserving unique records of the Moon's formation, volcanic evolution, impact history, tectonics and stress regime, regolith processes, volatile distribution, and interaction with the space environment.
- Local resources accessible from a location can be assessed to establish their utilisation potential and to develop the knowledge and capabilities needed to extract and process them.
- Habitation: Proximity to lunar pits and lava tubes would enable scientific investigations through access to subsurface stratigraphy. Access to such features would also allow investigations to assess

whether such locations might be used in the future as shelters for humans and equipment.

- **Environment:** Understanding surface interactions with the solar wind and radiation, including volatile implantation and regolith weathering, are essential for assessing environmental conditions. Coordinated measurements of plasma–regolith interactions, volatile-release processes, and exosphere dynamics provide critical insights into surface weathering, volatile transport, and plasma–surface coupling. Such investigations are not site specific but benefit from deployment at diverse locations.

- **Geophysics and astrophysics:** ROI should enable laser-based interferometric measurements for gravitational wave detection to bridge the frequency gap between ground- and space-based missions, with optimal performance dependent on low local seismic noise. Distributed networks of geophysical stations can probe the Moon's deep interior. The lunar far side is a unique location for radio measurements to observe the earliest epochs of the universe.

Figure 1: Locations of the 18 submissions received on the nearside of the Moon.

Key capabilities: Exploration of these regions should require surface mobility over several hundred kilometers, direct Earth communication, reliable power, subsurface access, and sample return capabilities.

Key Regions of Interest: Priority was given to infrastructure in mid-northern latitude regions on the lunar near side. These sites offer the best combination of geological diversity, resource potential, and operational feasibility (*Figure 2*).

**Aristarchus Plateau/
Montes Harbinger-Rimae Prinz**

- geologic diversity & ISRU potential (e.g., hydrated pyroclastic material)
- Procellarum KREEP Terrane
- potential subsurface access (e.g., lava tubes, pits) & reconstruction of the volcanic evolution
- youngest lunar mare basalts

Oriente Basin

- bridging near- and farside
- investigation of basin formation
- refinement of the lunar chronology (Oriente is the youngest lunar basin)
- geologically diverse & potential resources (e.g., hydrated pyroclastic material), but no KREEP material

Rima Bode/Mare Vaporum

- geologic diversity & ISRU potential (e.g., hydrated pyroclastic material)
- Procellarum KREEP Terrane material
- potential subsurface access (e.g., lava tubes, pits) & reconstruction of the volcanic evolution
- refinement of the lunar chronology (Copernicus & Eratosthenes crater material)

Figure 2: Most promising regions based on the submissions received and the workshop: Aristarchus Plateau & Montes Harbinger/Rima Prinz region, the Rima Bode-Mare Vaporum region, and the Orientale basin.

The nearside Procellarum KREEP (Potassium Rare Earth Elements and Phosphorus) Terrane (PKT) provides a unique scientific and strategic value. Two regions within the PKT stand out as the highest priorities due to their exceptional geological diversity and strong resource potential:

- The Aristarchus region – encompassing the Aristarchus Plateau, Vallis Schröteri, Montes Harbinger, and Rimae Prinz
- The Rima Bode region – encompassing Rima Bode and Mare Vaporum

Outside the PKT, the Orientale basin was identified as a strategic region to access due to its location on the western limb, straddling the nearside and far-side.

Polar regions are promising for exploration because they may offer “eternal light” for energy generation and operations as well as locations with stable water ice conditions and other valuable scientific opportunities. However, the amount, distribution and accessibility of local water ice and other volatiles remain uncertain. These uncertainties must be resolved through prospecting missions before establishing a long-term infrastructure in these areas.

Far side regions are scientifically compelling in particular as quiet locations for radioastronomy, geophysics and environmental studies. This might be considered as a longer-term option for a lunar infrastructure applying the lessons learned from experience on the nearside.

Conclusions: PKT regions appear to be the most favorable locations for a European-led lunar infrastructure by 2040, offering advantages in operational accessibility, safety, geological diversity, resource potential, habitation research, and scalability. Far-side sites, while less suitable for early infrastructure, provide uniquely quiet environments for astrophysics and geophysics and could be developed in a later phase. Interest in the lunar poles is driven by the possibility of water ice resources and favorable solar energy conditions, but current uncertainties mean that exploration should precede infrastructure development. Strategic decisions will also be needed about which resources Europe should prioritize for long-term access, while recognizing that some scientific investigations require instruments distributed across multiple lunar locations rather than a single base. Overall, a future lunar infrastructure will rely on centralized energy, robotics, shelter for scientific facilities, mobility across ~200 km large region with sample collection and return capability, supported by upcoming ESA initiatives such as Small Missions, commercial partnerships, and other new programs.

References: [1] Jaumann et al. (2012). *Planetary and Space Science*, 74(1), 15–41. [2] Crawford et al. (2015). *Progress in Physical Geography*, 39(2), 137–167. [3] van der Bogert et al. (2021). *The Planetary Science Journal*, 2(2), 84. [4] Carrer et al. (2024). *Nat. Astron.* 8, 1119–1126.